

The object as mediator: a pedagogical plan for museums dealing with anti-immigration discourses

El objeto como mediación: plan pedagógico para el museo frente a discursos antiinmigración

O objeto como mediador: um plano pedagógico para museus diante de discursos anti-imigração

Catalina Gayà Morla, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Barcelona. España, (catalina.gaya@uab.cat)

David Vidal Castell, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Barcelona. España, (david.vidal@uab.cat)

Cristina Garde Cano, Universitat Pompeu Fabra. Barcelona. España, (cristina.garde@upf.edu)

Laia Seró Moreno, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Barcelona. España, (laia.sero@autonoma.cat)

ABSTRACT | This article presents a pedagogical proposal for secondary schools, developed in the fishing district of Molinar in Palma by the Maritime Museum of Mallorca (MMM). The initiative aims to foster intergenerational and intercultural communication while challenging anti-immigration narratives. It forms part of a broader research project led by the museum throughout 2023 and 2024. Grounded in the Anthropology of Communication, the proposal explores how objects can be re-signified as artifacts by virtue of their status as symbolic constructs. In becoming artifacts, these objects resist accelerationist temporalities, decontextualization, and homogenization, and instead support the articulation of community-based meaning. The design of the proposal centers on 20 objects imbued with significance, each reflecting the memory of the local fishing community. When understood as mediating elements, these objects become tools for constructing shared meaning. Among them, ten are specifically used as catalysts for questions that seek to deconstruct dominant and socially accepted narratives around migration. The discussion considers how the project positions the museum as a space for dialogue and encounter, using its discursive power to intervene in one of the key challenges of the 21st century: transforming colonial discursive structures that underpin hate and anti-immigration rhetoric. In doing so, it aims to confront the cultural fundamentalism that sustains hegemonic narratives.

KEYWORDS: museums, anti-immigration discourse, mediation, pedagogical plan, artistic artifact

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RESUMEN | Este artículo presenta una propuesta pedagógica dirigida a institutos de secundaria, desarrollada en el barrio pesquero del Molinar de Palma para el Museo Marítimo de Mallorca (MMM). Su objetivo es fomentar la comunicación intergeneracional e intercultural y contrarrestar los discursos antiinmigración. La iniciativa forma parte de una investigación más amplia impulsada por el museo durante 2023 y 2024. Desde la perspectiva de la Antropología de la comunicación, se explora cómo los objetos pueden resignificarse como artefactos, en tanto que constructos simbólicos. El objeto devenido artefacto impugna las lógicas temporales aceleracionistas, la descontextualización y la homogeneización, y apela a la articulación comunitaria. La propuesta se articula en torno a 20 objetos cargados de sentido, representativos de la memoria de la comunidad pesquera del barrio. Al ser interpretados como elementos de mediación, estos objetos se transforman en artefactos que facilitan la construcción de significados compartidos. De ellos, diez son utilizados como catalizadores de preguntas destinadas a cuestionar el marco socialmente aceptado sobre la migración. En la discusión se analiza cómo el proyecto posiciona al museo como un espacio de diálogo y encuentro, desde el cual intervenir —gracias a su poder discursivo— en uno de los grandes desafíos del siglo XXI: transformar las estructuras coloniales del discurso que alimentan los relatos de odio y exclusión, y hacer frente al fundamentalismo cultural que ha sostenido los discursos hegemónicos.

PALABRAS CLAVE: museos, discurso antiinmigración, mediaciones, plan pedagógico, artefacto artístico.

RESUMO | Este artigo apresenta uma proposta pedagógica voltada para escolas secundárias desenvolvida para o bairro pesqueiro do Molinar de Palma para o Museu Marítimo de Maiorca (MMM). Seu objetivo é fomentar a comunicação intergeracional e intercultural, além de contrapor os discursos anti-imigração. A iniciativa integra uma pesquisa mais ampla, promovida pelo museu durante os anos de 2023 e 2024. A partir da perspectiva da Antropologia da Comunicação, explora-se como os objetos podem ser ressignificados como artefatos enquanto construções simbólicas. O objeto, ao tornar-se artefato, desafia as lógicas temporais aceleracionistas, a descontextualização e a homogeneização, ao mesmo tempo em que promove a articulação comunitária. A proposta baseia-se em 20 objetos carregados de significado, representativos da memória da comunidade pesqueira do bairro. Ao serem utilizados como elementos de mediação, esses objetos transformam-se em artefatos que facilitam a construção de significados compartilhados. Dentro deles, dez são empregados como catalisadores de questões destinadas a desconstruir o quadro socialmente aceito sobre a migração. Na discussão, analisa-se como o projeto posiciona o museu como um espaço de diálogo e encontro, capaz de intervir, a partir de seu poder discursivo, em um dos desafios mais relevantes do século XXI: transformar as estruturas discursivas coloniais do discurso que alimentam narrativas de ódio e exclusão, e confrontar o fundamentalismo cultural que estruturou os discursos hegemônicos.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: museus, discurso anti-imigração, mediações, plano pedagógico, artefato artístico

INTRODUCTION

Maritime museums are currently undergoing a thorough review of their narratives¹ (Croizet, 2021; Loran Gili, 2021; Anderson, 2023; Redman, 2022) and their role in processes of colonization (Wróblewska, 2022; Soares, 2023; Bril et al., 2024; Andrews, 2024) and the creation and agency of collective identities, both national and communal. These museums are agents that have historically disseminated colonial discourses (Smith, 2011; Curiel, 2015; Brown & Liguori, 2024) and now face the challenge of problematizing their role in the community while addressing the main concerns of the 2030 Agenda, such as quality education, the reduction of inequalities, the health of the seas and oceans, globalization, the disappearance of jobs in the primary sector and, undoubtedly, the mobility of people at sea. Due to their role in transmitting collective narratives — whether through permanent or temporary exhibitions or educational guides — these institutions have often perpetuated systems of domination that support and legitimize the violence associated with the logics of subordination, possession and dependency of the colonial system (Gayà Morlà et al., 2023). A system that is also nourished by a cultural fundamentalism, as defined more than two decades ago by Stolcke (2000), which sees the migrant as a threat to a supposedly homogeneous national and cultural identity — an identity constructed through the lens of an imaginary monoculturalism — as embodying a culture and identity different from that of the host country.

In museums, not only maritime ones, the need for restorative revision, understood as a process of recognition for restitution and reparation (Vergès, 2023), is increasingly evident as these institutions take up their positions as discursive actors (Alpers, 1991; Navarro Rodríguez, 2018; Pegno & Souffrant, 2024; Whitehead, 2024). “In their pursuit of neutrality (whereby neutrality merely maintains the status quo), museums are increasingly at risk of losing their relevance in contemporary and political society” (Procter, 2024, p. 19).

As early as the 1980s, this approach was proposed by the New Museology movement, which advocated a shift from a research and conservation-oriented practice to an institutional perspective that focuses on visitors (the public) and builds on these collections (Weil, 1999). The author famously summarized this

1. Although the word narrative is often used in English to refer to the ideological framework within which discourses are conducted, we refer to the totality of narrations, which always convey stories, i.e., shared ideological premises. We will then define metanarrative as a set of stories. It is thus assumed that a narrative is always based on a metanarrative that shapes a community's shared vision of the world (Gayà Morlà et al., 2022).

shift as “from being about something to being for someone” (p. 229), without in fact criticizing the archive or the privileges that sustain the collection (Vergès, 2023; Fornari, 2017) and relegating these experiences to the education or public departments, outside of communication or curation.

Since the attack on the World Trade Center in New York on September 11, 2001, the narrative on migration has been primarily framed by security and fear (Truax, 2023). The discourse on migration is no longer associated with work and the economy, but is framed in terms of terrorism and security (Puente et al., 2022). Narratives that link human mobility to criminal activities, natural disasters, and threats to the security of destination countries are constructed in the context of partisan or State discourse. This narrative is reproduced in the media, often without being contrasted or questioned (Truax, 2023; Román-Velázquez & Retis, 2021). Additionally, the absence of a representation of migrants in discursive frames other than those involving criminalization or illegality is particularly striking (Kastoryano et al., 2022).

The Maritime Museum of Mallorca (MMM) - member of the Association of Maritime Museums of the Mediterranean — is aware of its responsibility as an institution of discursive influence (MINOM, 2024) and takes up the challenge of amplifying urgent and current debates, including that of migration, by drawing on the experiences of the communities in the coastal neighborhoods and cities across Mallorca.

The recent creation of the museum in 2018 and the fact that it was done through a participatory process that involved the island’s maritime community from the outset are central to the museum’s commitment to act as a discursive actor that supports diverse, egalitarian and fair narratives. In doing so, the museum joins initiatives aimed at what Vergès (2023) describes as “rethinking the museum” – a critical reflection on the position from which the universal museum is constructed and legitimized. This article is the result of a research project carried out by the MMM itself in El Molinar, one of the coastal districts of the island’s capital, Palma, between 2023 and 2024.

The general objective of the research project, entitled *El Molinar, tela marinera*, is to recover the fishing memory of this neighborhood from the mid-20th century to the present day, in order to counteract the forgetting and emptiness that the identity narratives have turned into folklore. It also aims to promote a process of restitution to the citizens of Mallorca through various interventions (García Canclini & Martín Barbero, 2019), recognizing that the loss of identity, gentrification and community disengagement affecting El Molinar can be transferred to other gentrified cities (Cladera Salvà, 2021).

One of the interventions of the project that will be discussed in this article is a pedagogical proposal for secondary schools based on recovered objects that represent the memory of the fishing community of El Molinar. These objects, understood as mediating elements of the community's cultural experience, are transformed into artifacts for the articulation of meaning, in accordance with the perspective developed in the theoretical framework.

Based on the life stories collected during the ethnographic fieldwork in the neighborhood, 20 selected objects –considered as carriers of narratives and meanings– were used to create pedagogical worksheets designed to promote intergenerational and intercultural dialog. These worksheets facilitate the transition from object to artifact, activating processes of recognition and collaborative action that go beyond the fishing community itself.

Building on the coordinates of time, space and bodies –and the indicators identified therein– the aim is to develop a classroom intervention that enables young people to redefine and critically engage with the hegemonic narrative of migration.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: THE SENSE OF MEDIATION OF THE OBJECT, FROM THE THING ITSELF TO THE ARTIFACT

We have emphasized that this proposal is grounded in the need to move from the object or thing-in-itself to the artifact, i.e., to the symbolic manifestation of the thing that is constructed in tension with and by the subject. The tension between the knowing subject and the object is a recurring theme in various philosophical traditions. In the global West, Kant introduced the distinction between things as they are in themselves and the nature of things as we know them in the *Critique of Pure Reason* (2022) and warned of the dangers of ignoring this distinction (Martínez & Pelegrín, 2024).

Since then, Western philosophy has reconsidered its relationship to objecthood, to the thing, and redefined the way in which we appropriate its meaning. As Kant writes: "Until now it has been assumed that all our knowledge must correspond to objects; [...] let us try whether we cannot get on with metaphysics by assuming that objects should be governed by our knowledge" (Kant, 2022, p. 17). "If before Kant the gaze was directed at the thing, he proposes that we turn our attention to the subject and see how it structures its knowledge" (Martínez & Pelegrín, 2024, p. 79).

The result is Kant's synthesis between a deobjectified rationalism and a realist positivism: the origin of knowledge is undoubtedly in the thing itself, which exists as an unattainable and immeasurable noumenon, but the subject only perceives the manifestation of this thing for itself –what Kant calls the

phenomenon— according to its cognitive faculties, its receptivity and its a priori concepts. Martínez and Pelegrín claim: "Things themselves lack the capacity to constitute our experience" (2024, p. 80).

From a symbolic perspective, the fundamental aspect of an object is its ability to convey a narrative that transcends the information it provides. As Garí (2024) writes, "objects dispersed in a network or constellation function as extensions of people, expressing and disseminating their agency and configuring for the actors involved a distributed or shared personality that allows them to participate in social life" (p. 27). Furthermore, the object that has become an artifact challenges the accelerationist logic of time: "Through an object, memory can be woven and snatched from oblivion" [...]. In the object, the past ultimately coexists with the present in such a way that the temporal levels seem to merge and magically align" (Racionero, 2024).

The virtual context of non-things

In the digital culture of platforms, the materiality of objects —what German metaphysics from Kant (2022) to Han (2021) had called things— loses its meaning; according to Han, things either disappear or evoke indifference in the virtual digital culture of the platform. A world duplicated in virtual space and stored in the huge warehouses of giant online retailers such as Temu or Amazon. The Industrial Revolution, with its assembly lines, turned its attention to the thing. As Han writes, it "amplified and expanded the sphere of things [...] Digitalization brings the paradigm of things to an end" (Han, 2021, p. 15). Platform culture has caused a shift in the opposite direction. "Non-things displace things, we live in an intangible, clouded, spectral world, nothing is fixed" (Han, 2021, p. 13). Information, as a non-thing, covers the world of things with an impenetrable membrane (Han, 2021; Garde Cano, 2024).

Yet despite these processes of digital colonization of existence, the self encodes presences, memories and meanings in the objects it has constructed or stored in its environment as metonym and synecdoche of an experience of love, hate, disappointment or revelation. These artifacts function as mediating elements that enable us to appropriate contingency.

"The history deposited in things through long use gives them sentimental value" (Han, 2021, p. 28). We do this not only as individuals, but above all as members of a community: as a physical experience, community consists of glances that meet, voices that intersect, and bodies that share spaces and times. "Culture has its origins in the community. It transmits the symbolic values that produce a community" (Han, 2021, p. 31). Thus, the more we reduce objects to mere

commodities rather than artifacts, the more we impoverish cultural experience and weaken the sense of community.

From object to artifact

The anthropology of communication describes mediations as necessary instances for accessing the meaning of the world (Duch, 2018; Martín Barbero, 1987). These instances have an undeniable communal dimension, as people are denied direct access to meaning. In order to construct and express meaning, we need such mediations (Chillón & Duch, 2016), which are anchored and reproduced in what anthropology calls areas of transmission — family, school, neighborhood. Objects, for example, serve as vessels of narratives and meanings, unless they lose this capacity through the unraveling of the communal narrative and become mute material accidents. In this context, the category of mediation must be articulated alongside that of mediatization, considering that what remains after the performance of the evoked circumstance is the digital record, in this case photographs, videos and other materials capable of extending the communication of experience beyond the ethnographically observed subjects (Hjarvard, 2016; Hepp, 2022).

The theoretical perspective underlying this work is radically critical of the sharp distinction between object and subject, since various disciplines have established that the former is, to varying degrees, a symbolic construction of the latter. This process of meaning-making, which builds on a pre-existing materiality, is fundamentally semiotic and collective—intersubjective — as Barthes repeatedly emphasized. In *Mythologies* (1989) he describes the process he calls semiotization, through which societies become aware that all objects function as signs, "a social use added to the raw material" (p. 200).

In this sense, Foucault (1968) warned that object formation is a function of the knowledge-power apparatus articulated through discourse. For the French philosopher, objects are not "purely and simply things": rather, the task is to set things aside, to "de-presentify" them (p. 78). Pardo (2002) writes:

A discovery emerges: that every object, no matter how useful it may be, beyond the mere materiality or functionality that justifies its entry into society, carries with it the condition of being a signifier within a message that effectively circulates, even if its users are not aware of it (par. 2).

For all these reasons, and in the context of the collective memory and presence in which we find ourselves, this project proposed to call these objects artifacts, as they are symbolic constructs that serve as narrative motifs within the shared history of the community that goes beyond their materiality. When we present and re-present these artifacts and place them in a community-based context, we encourage the

recovery and reconnection with this forgotten narrative and facilitate the symbolic recapitalization of the objects for the community. The artifact becomes a catalyst for questions that challenge young people and, through guided reflection, serve to dismantle the socially accepted framework of migration. In this case, the question of how to transform intangible legacies –especially those that live primarily in the narrative of the community or what is left of it– into heritage is particularly relevant.

CONTEXT

According to the International Organization for Migration (Organización Internacional de las Migraciones, 2025), a total of 30,547 migrants died on their way across the Mediterranean to Europe between 2014 and 26 October 2024. The *Mare Nostrum* is behind us: it has become the *Mare Mortum*. According to the Balearic Institute of Statistics, 1,171,543 people live in the Balearic Islands, but almost half were born outside the four islands (Mallorca, Menorca, Ibiza and Formentera): 256,365 come from other Spanish autonomous communities and 219,684 from abroad. The largest foreign communities in the Balearic Islands are Moroccan (28,433), Italian (21,239), German (18,764), British (15,887), Colombian (13,166), Chinese (5,966), Ecuadorian (5,552) and Senegalese (4,886).

A public elementary school in any town on Mallorca, the largest of the Balearic Islands –whether in the capital Palma with 423,450 inhabitants or in a small village like Sant Joan with just over 2,000 inhabitants– reflects the cultural diversity and richness. These classes mix Catalan, Spanish, Arabic, Italian, German, English, Romanian, Mandarin, Wolof, and other languages. Children from many parts of the world fill the classrooms, while every week news arrives of shipwrecks and boats reaching the island's shores via the so-called Algerian route.

El Molinar, the neighborhood where this study is set, is a coastal area in Palma, Mallorca, marked by the history of migration past and present. In the 19th century, flour mills and fishing families lived there. Towards the end of the century, factories were built to extract and market gas, oil, electricity, and leather, all of which discharged pollutants into the sea. These industrial activities attracted people from other parts of the island. During the Spanish Civil War, the Francoist forces executed working-class men and women, and during the dictatorship the neighborhood was subject to severe repression (Garí, 2017). The ethnographic research carried out in the area revealed that most of the interviewees had arrived in the neighborhood during the Civil War as exiles or as part of the migration flows between mainland Spain and the island in the 1950s and 1960s. In this community, fishing has long been a trade involving migrants from the island itself, from the mainland and from other continents.

In the 1980s, when Palma became the hub of European tourism, El Molinar remained a neglected neighborhood stigmatized by sewage and drug trafficking. At the beginning of the 21st century, after the urban redevelopment of Palma's seafront promenade, which runs along El Molinar, the neighborhood became a desirable location for high-income residents (González-Pérez, 2020). Since then, the neighborhood's population has declined due to the influx of new, often transient residents who have purchased homes worth up to 17 million euros (Riera & Werner, 2024). This change has been accompanied by the loss of the fishing-related trade and the visual erasure and decontextualization of its material traces, as well as the migratory flows that have linked the Balearic Islands to Africa over the last two decades. Today, the fishing industry survives thanks to young Senegalese immigrants who were displaced from the African fishing grounds.

METHODOLOGY

This intervention aims to design a mediation tool — in this case a series of worksheets — that facilitates, through guided work, the construction of a process of collective engagement understood not only in relation to the group in the classroom, but also in relation to the inhabited territory. The artifact thus becomes a catalyst for issues that challenge young people and that aim to go beyond the socially accepted framework around important issues such as migration.

The mediation tool is built in two steps:

- *Step 1.* Recovering the mediating function of an object through a process of understanding the symbolic meaning attributed to it by a community of practice when it is named.
- *Step 2.* Enabling this object—as an artifact—to be endowed with meaning through debates centered on urgent issues to confront the socially accepted framework imposed by the hegemonic narrative and the stories that sustain it, thus generating new stories for a new narrative.

Methodological design: coordinates and indicators applied to the objects

The methodological design of the tool, which focuses on objects, is based on the indicators drawn from the conclusions of the research project *El Molinar, tela marinera*. These indicators are structured around the three coordinates through which we approach the stories underlying any narrative: time, space, and bodies. This perspective has already been applied in previous projects to challenge the hegemonic metanarrative and propose egalitarian, diverse, and inclusive narratives (Gayà Morlà et al., 2023, 2024). The indicators that serve as the starting point for the design of the tool are listed in table 1.

Coordinates	Indicators
Time	Life timelines Precarity Lack of generational continuity
Space	Conflict and care Borderless space Borderless sphere Borderless knowledge
Bodies	Diverse Productive Affectionate Communal Violated Exploited Normalized

Table 1. Indicators by research coordinate

Source: Own elaboration.

The methodological design includes three phases:

Phase 1. Object selection. This phase draws on the 19 semi-structured interviews conducted as part of the research project –ten male fishermen, a sailing instructor and a master boat builder, three female fishmongers, a female boatman, the wife of a fisherman, the granddaughter of a fishing business owner, and the granddaughter and daughter of a fishing family. From these interviews, the objects mentioned in the participants' stories are selected. This initial list of 20 objects will be discussed with community representatives in meetings to link each object to a research indicator. These sessions include special contributions from Antoni Josep Munar, 'Boliquet', resident of El Molinar, son of the last master shipbuilder of the neighborhood and a knowledgeable expert in the field, and Jaume Amengual, a master net maker and fisherman. A sample of ten objects was selected (table 2), representing the general indicators aligned with the coordinates of time, space, and bodies, but which are also useful for sparking a discussion on migration. In cases where more than one object is associated with a particular research-relevant finding, preference is given to objects already in the museum's collection, objects that members of the community are willing to donate to the museum, or objects that the museum can acquire by other means.

No.	Object
1	Oar
2	Jonquillo (Flexible wooden strip)
3	Family photo album
4	Llaüt Manuela (Traditional boat)
5	Princesa scale
6	Cross of the Order of Merit
7	Lantern
8	Basket
9	Outfall pipe
10	Polishing iron

Table 2. The ten selected objects

Source: Own elaboration.

Phase 2. Community stories connected to the objects. The interviews and life stories, as well as the working sessions from the object selection process, are reviewed, and narratives in which the community explains the 20 sample objects are selected, focusing on the ten objects most clearly associated with migration-related stories. These stories are approached using the narrative techniques of the interpretive genre of journalism. For some of the objects, it is also appropriate to include life stories, interviews or documentation from a previous research project conducted at the Maritime Museum of Barcelona (MMB) focused on the inclusion of women in the museum's narrative (Gayà Morlà & Seró Moreno, 2022). Each of the stories is built around a central theme. Once the stories are selected, a photograph is taken of the community members who feature in these stories holding the object.

Phase 3. Topics for debate related to migration. In the third phase, the worksheet that guides the mediation is designed. The categories in the worksheet link the 20 objects to the oral memory collected from various communities on the island and to narratives previously created by the MMM, as well as to several contemporary topics for reflection. Thus, while the communities' memory is made visible and embodied, the young people working with the worksheets are also involved in contemporary debates, so that the proposed mediation serves as an artifact for discussion. In the case of the worksheets for the ten objects that enable debate about migration, each object and its associated stories is linked to the identified hegemonic narrative that discursively mediates various identified sub-stories. These hegemonic narratives are challenged so that new narratives can be imagined that will form an alternative narrative. To this end, the seven key points for creating new narratives about human mobility from the Foundation for Research, Journalism and Migration (Carvajal et al., 2019) are considered.

RESULTS: WORKSHEETS WITH THE OBJECTS-ARTIFACTS

Results analysis

Table 3 shows how the ethnographic research indicators relate to the ten objects particularly associated with migration. It also shows how the testimonies build their narratives primarily on the basis of a particular theme around each object. In addition, the table shows which stories from the hegemonic narrative on migration are brought into play with each object and under which alternative narratives this discourse can be challenged to construct a new one that conveys new narratives for the fishing community, but also for young people and citizens in general.

No.	Object	Indicators	Theme or focus	Hegemonic narratives	Alternative narratives
1	Oar	<i>Time</i> : precarity <i>Body</i> : exploited	Smuggling	They/we	Collective identity: we are all migrants
2	Jonquillo (flexible wooden strip)	<i>Time</i> : lack of generational continuity	Lack of generational continuity	Migrant as passive subject	Migrants as active subjects
3	Family photo album	<i>Space</i> : borderless space, borderless spheres, borderless knowledge	People-boat ratio	They/we	We are all migrants
4	<i>Llaüt</i> Manuela	<i>Bodies</i> : productive	Death	Migrant as passive subject	Migrants as active subjects
5	Princesa Scale	<i>Bodies</i> : normative	Role of women	They/we	Collective identity: we are all migrants
6	Cross of the Order of Merit	<i>Bodies</i> : community-oriented, diverse	Solidarity	Securitization	Welcome/hospitality
7	Lantern	<i>Bodies</i> : violated	European regulations	They/we	Collective identity: we are all migrants
8	Basket	<i>Time</i> : life timelines	Family/clan	Securitization	Welcome/hospitality
9	Outfall pipe	<i>Space</i> : conflict and care	Pollution	Migration as something avoidable	Migration as a process
10	Polishing iron	<i>Bodies</i> : affectionate	Affections	Migration as something avoidable	Migration as a process

Table 3. Coordinates, approaches, and narratives identified around the objects

Source: Own elaboration.

From this work we were able to derive the narratives that explain the different coordinates and their indicators for the fishing community.

Therefore, regarding time:

- *Life timelines.* Biological, intimate, and communal times emerge. When listening to the community, the circularity of time emerges, and the narrative becomes anchored in a specific context.
- *Precarity.* Lifetime is associated with the need to make a living to survive in their territory, from childhood to death.
- *Lack of generational continuity.* They feel bound to a finite time and see themselves as the last representatives of the trade.

Regarding space:

- *Conflict and care.* The way space is narrated includes conflict, care, violence, and everyday life.
- *Borderless space.* There is no distinction between land space and sea space; actions and processes cut across both.
- *Borderless spheres.* There is no division between public and private or intimate space: they are narrated as a continuum.
- *Borderless knowledge.* Knowledge transcends all spaces.

Regarding bodies:

- *Diverse bodies.* There is a diversity of bodies: all available people are needed.
- *Productive bodies.* Bodies remain productive throughout life. Trade prevails over formal education.
- *Affectionate bodies.* Emotions emerge and are externalized: fear, tears, mutual support, physical contact...
- *Community body.* There is a shared body –that of the community– that protects and isolates its members, with rules that must be followed; otherwise, one is cast out. There is also a familial body, embodied in a fishing clan, with its own survival strategies.
- *Violated bodies.* These bodies are described as being controlled and violated by the system. Community members feel expelled from their neighborhood. In contrast, they recall a past defined by the possibility of autonomy.

- *Exploited body.* The body is their working tool, and they are assigned different tasks depending on the body they were born with –except for net-making, a mixed-gender activity.
- *Bodies shaped by gender roles.* Women are the keepers of memory. It is the woman who joins the clan without having been born into it, and she ultimately becomes its guardian. Women also serve as managers of the enterprise.

After the analysis, we can draw some conclusions about how seafarers construct collective narratives and link them to the selected objects (table 4) in the specific context of migration. In contrast to the hegemonic media narrative, which tends to portray migrants through a dichotomy of them versus us, or as passive subjects in need of help, the new narrative provides a framework to understand migration as a process rooted in welcome and hospitality, based on the premise that migrants are active subjects and that, ultimately, all citizens are migrants.

This perspective allows for a deeper understanding and recognition of the scars that migration leaves behind, as well as the various reasons that drive people to migrate, including love or climate change. The testimonies of the seafarers make us reflect on the disappearance of natural ecosystems. Fishing, a trade that requires teamwork and strong family ties, fosters networks of solidarity that link migration and urban life; the space we inhabit becomes both refuge and home.

This collective recognition strengthens political agency to confront the deaths of migrants in the Mediterranean. The recovery of shared memory through objects provides a framework to reflect on the militarization of borders and the criminalization of migrants. The role of women taking on the role of guardians of intangible heritage is also particularly linked to forms of motherhood in resistance in the context of migration.

All of these narratives, made actionable through an alternative narrative, are proposed as topics for debate in the classroom, in contrast to the socially accepted view of migration shaped by the dominant media narrative. The following table summarizes the stories that underlie both the hegemonic discourse on migration and the alternative narrative that emerges from the life stories collected as part of the ethnographic research.

Hegemonic narrative (and the stories it conveys)	Alternative narrative (and the stories it conveys)
They/we	Collective identity (we are all migrants/I am a migrant)
Migration as a problem	Cultural diversity as richness and strength
Migrant as a passive subject in need of help	Migrant as an active subject
Securitization: fear/militarization/crime/security	Hospitality/welcome
Migration as something avoidable	Migration as a process

Table 4. Migration from the perspective of hegemonic and alternative narratives

Source: Own elaboration based on Carvajal et al. (2019).

Worksheets: the mediation tool

Based on the methodology, we designed worksheets (Table 5) for the ten objects that will help us transition from object to artifact –meaning, a guide with a series of steps to recover the mediating function of an object. The worksheet should enable the object –as artifact– to be meaningful in the everyday lives of those engaging with it. The mediation exercise using the worksheet will follow a unidirectional, step-by-step structure. Specifically, ten of the 20 worksheets (figures 1, 2, and 3) will be essential for facilitating discussion on migration. The proposed steps are:

- Step 1. Observing the photograph of the isolated object.
- Step 2. Reading the technical description.
- Step 3. Asking the mediation questions proposed in the tool, which link the object to the everyday lives of those engaging with the guide.
- Step 4. Observing the image of the person alongside the object.
- Step 5. Reading the related stories.
- Step 6. Asking the mediation questions proposed in the tool that connect the specific object to migration.

Object	
Photograph	<i>Presentation of the object:</i> initial approach through descriptive categories (name, photograph, and brief description).
Description	
Mediation questions	<i>Guiding questions for mediation:</i> these are questions directed at the object that go beyond its functionality. They invite an initial articulation between the object, its meaning, and significance for both the community of practice and for the individual engaging with the worksheet.
Image of mediation	<i>Image representing mediation:</i> this is a photograph that implicitly or explicitly shows the object and one of the people whose voice will appear in the next section to illustrate the perspective associated with the object.
Artifact	<i>Mediation stories:</i> oral recollections are recovered from the community of practice that relate specifically to the perspective associated with the object. These narratives are presented with a title, an introduction and, finally, three to four first-person narratives by members of the community to emphasize the collective and polyphonic nature of the communities' memory.
Contemporary debate on issues related to the artifact	<i>List of contemporary debates:</i> three to five key themes to stimulate discussions that link the proposed mediation to the everyday lives of those who use the sheet.

Table 5. Proposed worksheet for identified objects

Source: Own elaboration.

Image 1. Worksheet. Jonquillo²

Source: Own elaboration.

2.A rounded strip used to trace the curved lines of a boat and shape the planks, among other things. It is a very simple piece, but indispensable for shipwrights.

Image 2. Worksheet. Oar

Source: Own elaboration.

Image 3. Worksheet. Decoration

Source: Own elaboration.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION: CONNECTING EXPERIENCES

The MMM’s goal of re-evaluating conventional museological practices and addressing a community challenge –such as identity diversity in a marginalized community– involves the development and implementation of mediation tools to promote community interaction. The structure of the methodological framework is itself an artifact, just as the museum becomes an artifact when it recognizes the need for restorative revision and, drawing on its position as a discourse-influencing actor,

enables and develops narrative methods that challenge hegemonic discourses, in this case that of migration. For museums, this shift means positioning themselves as sites of dialog and encounter, making their voices heard (Solnit, 2023), and using their discursive power to address one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century: changing the discursive colonial structures that give rise to anti-immigration and hate speech discourses –in other words, confronting the cultural fundamentalism that has shaped hegemonic narratives.

Based on the premise that the most important aspect of an object from a symbolic point of view is its ability to tell a story beyond factual information, the project uses ten selected objects and the texts that accompany them– to show that the sea is no longer a deadly border that divides, but becomes a space that connects experiences. At the same time, it makes it possible to tell the story of migration from a community-based perspective. Humans, despite their ever-changing nature – or precisely because of it– can regain a sense of unity through their relationship with the material presence of the object, which helps to anchor us as the ambiguous and in-motion beings that we are (Duch, 2018).

The object reclaims its role as a medium and acts as a catalytic artifact for stories, experiences, connections, and ultimately community. This work strengthens the spaces of transmission and the structures of hospitality –family, city, association– in which symbolic mediations function. These spaces have been weakened by the development of the industrial media culture of the last century and are seriously threatened by the techno-capitalist culture of the digital platform (Garde Cano, 2022).

Thus, the objects –narrated by previous generations through stories that recover communal notions of time and space and place the body at the center are redefined across generations. They transcend the traditional notion of heritage as they speak of affections, emotions, conflicts, and bodies and connect to the oral memory of the community of practitioners. This oral memory transcends accelerated time, decontextualized spaces, and homogenized bodies. The starting premise is that an object can tell a story from a symbolic perspective that goes beyond the factual information it provides — for example, what is written on a museum label — and that it can become an artifact that connects meaning and narrative through bodies and embodied experiences.

In this regard, the object offers a recognition of ancestral human, factual and communal knowledge as well as an affective dimension: it becomes a means of acknowledging the object in contemporary debates and transcending the socially accepted frame of migration to create new alternative narratives in and out of the classroom.

In fact, the artifact accompanies the community in a process of transformation. Through the artifact, the community recovers connections, builds its collective memory –not just the familial or individual one–, and recognizes itself as a community. This empowerment takes place on two levels: on an endogenous one, when the members of the community build a memory and begin to claim the public space for themselves, and on an exogenous one, when the community realizes that its history enables the rest of the island to face common challenges. This change is only possible because a place with symbolic power –the museum– amplifies the voice of the community.

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ABOUT THE AUTHORS

CATALINA GAYÀ MORLA.

 [0000-0001-6190-6824](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6190-6824)

Ph.D. in Communication and lecturer at the Department of Media, Communication, and Culture of the UAB, where she teaches Cultural Policies in the master's program and Journalistic Writing in the undergraduate program. She is a researcher in the SGR group Body and Textuality. Authorship and Subjectivities in Construction. She led a study on the perception of patriarchal violence and equality for the Balearic Women's Institute (2018) and the project Dona'm la Mar of the Maritime Museum of Barcelona (2019–2020).

DAVID VIDAL CASTELL

 [0000-0002-8178-6580](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8178-6580)

Associate professor at the Department of Media, Communication, and Culture at the UAB, journalist, and literary critic. Head of the master's degree in Literary Journalism at the UAB, he was head of the Media Department (2019–2022), coordinator of the Journalism degree, vice-dean of the Faculty, and deputy director of the Santa Mònica Art Center (2010–2012). Ph.D. in Communication (Alteritat i presència, 2002). The Catalan Audiovisual Council awarded him the research prize for El malson de Chandos.

CRISTINA GARDE CANO

 [0000-0002-8700-9686](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8700-9686)

Lecturer at the Department of Communication of the Universitat Pompeu Fabra and in the master's degree in Philosophy for Contemporary Challenges at the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya. Ph.D. in Media, Communication, and Culture (2022, awarded at the XXXIV CAC Awards), holds a degree in Journalism, and a bachelor in Art and Design. She has worked for El País, El Periódico and Nació, as a correspondent in Brussels for CAN, and as editor-in-chief of Social.cat. She is a research assistant in the DigiDoc group at UPF.

LAIA SERÓ MORENO

 [0000-0001-8886-5882](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8886-5882)

She examines social issues from the perspective of narrative and ethnography through the lens of documentary literature, collective memory, and depatriarchalization. She is the web editor of the newspaper ARA and a researcher at UAB. She holds a degree in Journalism and a master in Anthropology and Ethnography from the Universidad de Barcelona (UB). She has participated in and co-directed gender-related research projects for institutions such as the Museu Marítim de Barcelona, the Museu Marítim de Mallorca and the Institut Balear de la Dona.